

Comprehensive Survey of the Cryptographic Framework for Data Security

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Abstract–Due to the growing prevalence of cyberattacks and privacy breaches in the modern digital world, ensuring the secrecy, authenticity, and integrity of sensitive data has become increasingly critical. Traditional cryptosystems face mounting challenges from both advanced classical computing and emerging quantum computing capabilities, which threaten to compromise existing encryption frameworks. In this paper we discussed data security and its limitations.

Keywords–Encryption, Decryption, Cryptographic models, data security, integrity

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of information age, specifically every field utilizes the communication and information that information sharing, managing and privacy preserving is the important role in the cyber space. This communication enables people to easily connect with the world and effortlessly manage the devices using Internet of Things (IoT) technology which significantly revolutionized their life [1]. This connectivity ranges from sharing of information in various fields like medical, confidentiality data, banking information and several business privacy data in the cyber space. Nevertheless, the key anxiety for communication is the security in the cyber space. In last few years, the origination information attacking has increased. The attackers are trying to steal the important data of the organization, banking etc. The data stolen is modified and manipulated by the attackers for their own benefits, which leads to a great loss for the owner of the organization and people [2].

The most essential thing is the protection of the confidential data over the cyber space from the attacker which is secured by using cryptography. Encryption and decryption processes form the base of the data security used by Cryptography techniques. The encryption process converts the original readable text into different format such as cipher text before data is shared [3]. Decryption is the process of converting the cipher text into original readable data after receiving the confidential data. The cryptography uses the secret private key, public key for encrypting and decrypting the data. The original text is transformed to unreadable information and is recovered in the decryption process [4]. The Lightweight cryptography algorithms protecting the data such as Elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) and RSA algorithm, data encryption standard (DES), advanced encryption standard (AES), and triple DES (3DES) etc. DES, 3DES and AES techniques are not suitable for the encryption and decryption of images as they are resource constrained devices. [5-6].

The ECC is an asymmetric-key algorithm that uses 256-bit key for encrypting and decrypting the 128-bit original data providing high security with small keys. RSA algorithm is a public key encryption algorithm that uses 3024-bit key to encrypt and decrypt the 128-bit size of information providing the similar level of security. [7-8]. In AES algorithm, substitution bytes (S-Box) play a crucial role in creating confusion against unauthorised access of the text but it does not completely prevent it. The second order one-dimensional reversible cellular automata overcome issues of unauthorized access in cyber space [9]. Various cryptography protocols play a significant role in the data security fields, nevertheless most of the existing developed cryptography protocols have defects and vulnerabilities. These defects are needed to be identified in the protocols to increase the secure data sharing. Some security properties are must and rigorous implementation in cryptography algorithm is required for improving the security. Theorem Proving is a very difficult method which is different from the traditional security detection method and it offers the security in identifying the object required verification. Logic of events (LoET-E) cryptography protocol lacks corresponding axioms and the rules and it provides guarantee to the correctness, original axioms validity, integrity and ensure event classes consistency in the proof process. This LoET cryptography protocol is very much useful in reducing the redundancy and complexity and extending the provable range of cryptography protocol.[10]

To check the confidentiality and authenticity in the public key encryption technique, verifying network protocols security properties, different logics like Protocol Composition Logic (PLC) and Interactive Probabilistic Dependency Logic (IPDL) are used. [11]. The data is protected from various kinds of attacks like the linear cryptanalysis attacks, brute-force attacks and differential cryptanalysis attacks the using analysis cellular automata and it also rectifies the confusion and diffusion properties over the cyber space [12]. The cellular automation selects the key configuration used for encryption process, the number of iterations used in the encryption and decryption of data. The cryptography algorithms improve the robustness in data transmission using these iterations and the key configurations. The one-dimensional cellular automation effectively encrypts huge amount of data so that images are encrypted using this technique [13]. The cellular automata, a highly distributed and parallel system, which pose the complicated behaviours is used to create the sequence in many ways. For huge amount of data encryption, Cellular automata with chaos techniques are used [14]. Cellular automata protect the data from the statistical attack and differential attack [15].

II. RESEARCH GAP

The analysis indicates that, following an extensive review of the literature from numerous research articles, the weaknesses in the earlier studies are identified. Consequently, a system's overall security will be jeopardised. Integrity, confidentiality, and verification issues cannot all be resolved simultaneously using the conventional cryptographic approach. The literature pays insufficient attention to the efficacy of important management practices, which are crucial for maintaining security in practical deployments. Furthermore, not enough studies have been done to determine how resistant current cryptographic techniques are to novel assaults. Traditional schemes, however, were susceptible to internal attacks.

III. MOTIVATION FOR THE WORK

Cryptography constitutes a foundational discipline within the realm of computer science, assuming a pivotal role in safeguarding sensitive information during its transmission and storage. Encryption and decryption techniques serve as the core of cryptography, facilitating the secure conveyance and retrieval of data across diverse digital platforms. Nevertheless, the creation and execution of efficient encryption and decryption methodologies confront an array of complexities and considerations. The realm of cryptographic algorithms necessitates fortifications against the increasingly sophisticated adversaries' attacks. The greatest challenge is to formulate effective encryption and decryption approaches that prevent data attacks, differential cryptanalysis, and other advanced tactics. Hence, the present research addresses the challenges related to data security within the cryptography domain, by fostering more robust, streamlined, and flexible cryptographic methodologies.

IV. OBJECTIVES

Presenting an effective data security.

Incorporating better data security and facilitating secure data interchange using an effective set of cellular automaton rules.

V. DATA SECURITY TECHNIQUES

These days, data security is essential. Online attacks are growing in number in tandem with the expansion of online transactions. Certain strategies are developed to safeguard data transmission in order to prevent hacking or unwanted access [19]. These methods are:

Cryptography

Some consider cryptography a science of protecting information through conversion into an unreadable format, which assures that only the authorized parties would have access to contents in original form [10]. The conversion process consists of:

- **Encryption:** Encryption refers to algorithms and keys that switch plain text (unencrypted data, or an unencrypted file) into unreadable form (ciphertext).
- **Decryption:** Reverting ciphertext back to plaintext using corresponding keys.

Cryptography plays a critical role in safeguarding data confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity. It automatically associates with different security protocols, such as SSL or TLS, for protected web communications and end-to-end encryption for messaging applications.

a) *Steganography*

Steganography entails hiding a message or file or image inside another medium such that no one would suspect the existence of the hidden message. While cryptography is intended to obscure the content of a message, steganography serves to hide the very existence of the message. Well-known techniques comprise embedding text into an image or audio file by altering insignificant bits, making detection very difficult without analytical tools. More often than not, this technique is combined with cryptography, thereby providing an additional level of security.

b) *Digital Watermarking*

Digital watermarking is the procedure of embedding a unique identifier or code into digital content of any kind, such as pictures, sound, or video, to claim ownership, authenticate, or track distribution [5]. These watermarks may either be:

- **Visible:** Clearly noticeable marks, like logos or text overlays.
- **Invisible:** Embedded within the content in a manner imperceptible to human senses but detectable by specialized software.

Digital watermarking represents a copyright protection measure, a means of forensic tracking, and verification of integrity of digital media. This prevents unauthorized copying and distribution, thus making it possible for concerned content creators or rights holders to exercise some control over their intellectual properties.

5.1. *Cryptography*

The encoding of data or information is the fundamental postulate of a cryptography system so that an unauthorized person cannot fully comprehend its meaning and the information is kept confidential. Using cryptography to send data over an unprotected channel, like the internet, or making sure that unauthorized users cannot decipher what they are viewing in the event that they have obtained the data, are two of its most popular applications. The process of hiding the plaintext is called "encryption," and the encrypted plaintext is called "ciphertext." In cryptography, the hidden information is typically referred to as "plaintext." A collection of guidelines referred to as "encryption algorithms" carry out this operation. The encryption algorithm is supplied with an "encryption key," as input along with the data, in the typical encryption process. With the right "decryption key," the receiving party can recover the data using a "decryption algorithm".

5.1.1. *Types of Cryptography*

Cryptography was initially done by hand using manual methods. Although the implementation was improved in the early days, the fundamental architecture remained mostly unchanged. Nowadays, as everything is dependent on technology and computers, cryptography is likewise done via computers to protect our data. Symmetric key [6] cryptography and asymmetric key cryptography are two methods of using computers to carry out operations and algorithms [8,9]. Basically, there are two kinds of cryptography depending on how the system performs encryption and decryption [4]:

- Symmetric Key Cryptography
- Asymmetric Key Cryptography

5.1.2. *Symmetric Key Cryptography*

Another name for symmetric key cryptography is shared key or secret-key cryptography. Both the sender and the recipient use the same key for encryption and decryption in this kind of system. The key is self-certified, which is in accordance with the self-certification procedure. It is necessary to communicate the key in secret. The attacker can quickly decipher the encrypted message if it is compromised. Because it offers speedier service while consuming fewer resources, this kind of encryption approach is necessary. To date, symmetric key cryptography has been described by a number of different algorithms. These include Blowfish, DES, 3DES, and AES.

5.1.3. Asymmetric Key Cryptography

With this process, we will encrypt it using the public key of the recipient, but decrypt it through the private key belonging to the recipient [3,15]. This feature denotes the use of digital signatures to certify the keys rather than the self-certification approach. Thus, this secure system provides superior authentication with better practicality when privacy is maintained. Encryption like this can be done through various methods of doing so, including the Digital Signature Algorithm, Diffie-Hellman, ECC, and RSA.

5.2. Modern Cryptography Concepts

In a nutshell, modern cryptography will be the science behind secure digital communications, such as privacy, data integrity, authentication, and non-repudiation mechanisms [16]. It is actually the opposite of classical cryptography, which only used simple substitution and transposition techniques, going as far as specifying mathematically complex public key mechanisms and digital certificates to keep information exchanges safe over open and untrusted networks. In addition to envelopes that also define other protocols and standards for securing data in real time, sensitive environments like financial systems, health care, e-governance, and cloud systems include many others. Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) within Certificateless Public-key Cryptography, each proposes resolutions on several issues, such as key management and identity assurance, in distributed systems [18].

5.2.1. Known-Plaintext Attack

The assailant has at least one pair: a plaintext and a corresponding ciphertext in a Known-Plaintext Attack (KPA). Then by analysing these known pairs, the attacker will try to get hold of the encryption key or predict how other plaintext messages would be encrypted, compromising future communications.

5.2.2 Chosen-Plaintext Attack

The assailant can select arbitrary plaintexts and obtain their corresponding ciphertexts under an unknown key in a Chosen-Plaintext Attack (CPA). This access allows the assailant to study the encryption process and potentially deduce the secret key or find patterns that lead to partial or full decryption of other messages.

5.2.3 Man-in-the-Middle Attack

A Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) Attack involves an opponent secretly intercepting and possibly altering communication between two parties without their knowledge. The attacker can eavesdrop, modify, or inject false messages, making it seem as though the two legitimate parties are communicating securely when, in reality, the attacker controls the conversation.

5.2.4 Side-Channel Attack

A Side-Channel Attack exploits physical or implementation-related information such as timing information, power consumption, electromagnetic emissions, or even sound that is leaked during the encryption or decryption process. By analysing these side effects, assailants can infer secret keys or sensitive data without directly breaking the cryptographic algorithm itself.

5.2.5 Brute Force Attack

A systematical trial of every possible key combination until the correct one is found is involved in a Brute Force Attack. While it guarantees success if enough time and computational power are available, strong encryption algorithms with adequately large key spaces make brute-force attempts remarkably infeasible in practice.

5.3. Existing Public Key Cryptosystems and Limitations

Public key cryptosystems form the backbone of modern secure communications, enabling key exchange, digital signatures, and secure encryption. Many existing cryptosystems are broadly accepted, yet each one has limitations in security, efficiency, and resistance to newer quantum threats. The main systems are:

5.3.1 RSA-Based Cryptosystems

One of the earliest and most widely used public key algorithms is RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman) is. It relies on the computational difficulty of factoring large composite numbers. RSA supports the encryption, digital signatures, and secure key exchange. However, it requires large key sizes (2048 bits or more) for sufficient security, leading to slower performance. RSA is highly susceptible to quantum attacks using Shor's algorithm.

5.3.2 Elliptic Curve Cryptography

Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) achieves almost similar security with smaller key sizes and is a more efficient replacement for the RSA processor. The complexity of the elliptic curve discrete logarithm problem (ECDLP) is how ECC got its name. Wire communication issues, particularly internet applications, mobile devices, and IoT, commonly favour ECC. All the same, it would not perform well in a quantum environment while ECC has demonstrated excellent performance. Side-channel attacks can still exploit implementation errors [17, 20].

5.3.3. Lattice-Based Cryptography

It uses the intractability of lattice problems like the shortest vector problem to build encryption and signature schemes. Among the post-quantum families of encryption, it is considered the strongest because of its robustness against classical as well as quantum adversaries. However, typical lattice schemes suffer from larger ciphertext and key sizes, which affect performance as well as storage efficiency.

5.3.4. Limitations in Existing Approaches

Most cryptosystems currently in operation have proven strong against threats from traditional computing, but they often suffer from limitations concerning scalability and efficiency, disadvantage them in terms of quantum resilience. Quantum algorithms such as Shor's, can break both RSA and ECC whereas lattice-based schemes are quantum-safe but have some associated costs in terms of larger keys and higher computational complexity. Key management, secure implementations, and protection against side-channel attacks continue to haunt public key infrastructures as one of the biggest challenges [17].

5.3.5. Motivation for the Study

This essay traces the growth of information assurance. During the present digital age, the spiraling usage of digital media in terms of text, image, audio, and video has tremendously increased worries about the security of sensitive information in transit across open, unsecured networks worldwide or the Internet. The unauthorized access, theft, and manipulation risks seem to be continually mounting, and thus there is a need for the development of highly robust and secure communication frameworks. Cryptographic techniques have stood for long as the base for protecting the confidentiality and integrity of data as well as privacy in enabling secure message exchanges using encryption keys. In fact, encryption in attaining or making data secure has always been a basic requirement across numerous applications in real life, including financial services applications, health or healthcare applications, military communication applications, and those applications based on cloud infrastructures.

Nonetheless, conventional identity authentication methods have mostly depended upon certificate-based infrastructures that complicate operations, adding possible security weaknesses and limitations to scalability. Cryptographic systems must now prove resilient against quantum-capable adversaries; hence the need has been most critical.

VI. CONTRIBUTION OF PROPOSED SCHEMES

The key contribution of this study is the design of a novel encryption scheme that synergistically combines graph-theoretic encryption strategies with evolutionary optimization for key selection and an enhanced key exchange protocol, resulting in a highly secure, efficient, and scalable cryptographic system suitable for safeguarding sensitive digital data against emerging security threats [16].

VII. SUMMARY

This paper effectively introduces data security. The significance of data security in defining modern digital architecture systems is brought out with respect to the role that data security plays in safeguarding sensitive information. Confidentiality, integrity, availability, authentication, and non-repudiation are the fundamental data security principles discussed alongside the threats that target the information, such as ciphertext-only, brute-force, and side-channel attacks. It also addresses traditional and contemporary data protection mechanisms like cryptography and steganography plus some digital watermarks, focusing on cryptography, which is described in two broad approaches: symmetric and asymmetric schemes with public key infrastructures, moving next to advanced paradigms such as Isogeny-based cryptography and DNA-based identity encryption. Furthermore, it identified the limitations of widely used cryptosystems like RSA, ECC, and lattice-based cryptography against modern and quantum threats. To overcome these challenges, the proposed research integrating Isogeny-based Edwards curves, DNA-based identity encryption, and a tri-level certificateless handshake mechanism was introduced, along with its motivation, objectives, contributions, and the overall structure of the thesis. Building on this foundation, the next chapter conducts an extensive literature survey, critically analyzing existing models, identifying their strengths and limitations, and pinpointing research gaps to justify the relevance and novelty of the proposed encryption framework.

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